

Comprehensive approach to the treatment of heart failure: integrating cardiology into medical care

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Abstract

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Heart failure (HF) is one of the most common and serious diseases of the cardiovascular system, characterised by the inability of the heart to provide adequate blood supply to the tissues of the body. Effective treatment of this condition requires a multidisciplinary approach that includes not only cardiological measures, but also the integration of the efforts of various specialists.

The present work is devoted to the study of a comprehensive approach to the treatment of heart failure, including modern methods of cardiology, pharmacotherapy, surgical interventions, rehabilitation and lifestyle changes in patients. This approach considers such aspects as pharmacological treatment (modern standards of heart failure therapy, including the use of ACE inhibitors, beta-blockers, mineral corticoid receptor antagonists and

drugs aimed at improving myocardial contractile function), non-medication methods (the role of rehabilitation programmes, lifestyle correction, nutrition and physical activity control), innovative technologies (the use of modern diagnostic and therapeutic methods, such as the following

This study emphasizes the importance of an integrated approach in the treatment of heart failure and demonstrates the need for continuous coordination between different specialists to improve the effectiveness of treatment and the quality of life of patients.

Keywords: heart failure, integrated approach, cardiology, pharmacotherapy, rehabilitation, surgical treatment, pacemaker implantation, mechanical circulatory support, multidisciplinary team, lifestyle modification.

Resumen

La insuficiencia cardíaca (IC) es una de las enfermedades más comunes y graves del sistema cardiovascular, caracterizada por la incapacidad del corazón para proporcionar un suministro adecuado de sangre a los tejidos del cuerpo. El tratamiento eficaz de esta afección requiere un enfoque multidisciplinario que incluya no sólo medidas cardiológicas, sino también la integración de los esfuerzos de varios especialistas.

El presente trabajo está dedicado al estudio de un enfoque integral para el tratamiento de la insuficiencia cardíaca, incluidos métodos modernos de cardiología, farmacoterapia, intervenciones quirúrgicas, rehabilitación y cambios en el estilo de vida de los pacientes. Este enfoque considera aspectos como el tratamiento farmacológico (estándares modernos de tratamiento de la insuficiencia cardíaca, incluido el uso de inhibidores de la ECA, betabloqueantes, antagonistas de los receptores de corticoides minerales y fármacos destinados a mejorar la función contráctil del miocardio), métodos no farmacológicos (el papel de la rehabilitación programas, corrección del estilo de vida, control de la nutrición y la actividad física), tecnologías innovadoras (el uso de métodos modernos de diagnóstico y terapéuticos, como los siguientes

Este estudio enfatiza la importancia de un enfoque integrado en el tratamiento de la insuficiencia cardíaca y demuestra la necesidad de una coordinación continua entre diferentes especialistas para mejorar la efectividad del tratamiento y la calidad de vida de los pacientes.

Palabras clave: insuficiencia cardíaca, abordaje integrado, cardiología, farmacoterapia, rehabilitación, tratamiento quirúrgico, implantación de marcapasos, soporte circulatorio mecánico, equipo multidisciplinario, modificación del estilo de vida.

Introduction

Heat failure (HF) is one of the most common and serious pathologies of the cardiovascular system, affecting millions of people worldwide. This condition is accompanied by a decrease in the functional ability of the heart to pump blood, which leads to insufficient blood supply to organs and tissues¹. HF significantly worsens the quality of life of patients and is associated with high mortality. The progressive nature of the disease requires continuous monitoring and correction of therapeutic measures.

The treatment of heart failure has undergone significant changes over the past decades, leading to improved clinical outcomes. The introduction of modern pharmacological agents, the development of highly effective surgical techniques, as well as progress in rehabilitation and monitoring of patients' health contribute to improved survival and quality of life of patients. However, the maximum effectiveness of treatment is achieved only with a comprehensive approach, which includes the integration of cardiology into general medical care and close interaction between physicians of different specialties².

The present work explores different aspects of the integrated approach to the treatment of heart failure, with emphasis on the need for multidisciplinary collaboration, the use of modern technology and the development of individualized treatment strategies for each patient.

Materials and methods

The following research methods were applied during the preparation of the article. The analysis of scientific literature implied a thorough study and systematization of current data on the problem of heart failure. Comparative analysis allowed comparing different methods of heart failure treatment, including pharmacological, surgical and rehabilitation approaches, as well as their effectiveness. Comparison of international guidelines and treatment protocols will also provide an opportunity to identify the best practices.

Generalization of data from various sources allowed to form a holistic view of the integrated approach. Synthesis of information from different fields of medicine (cardiology, therapy, rehabilitation) will allow developing recommendations on the integration of approaches in the treatment of heart failure.

The use of a systemic approach helped to consider heart failure not as an isolated disease, but as part of a complex clinical picture, including multifactorial causes and influencing factors (co morbidities, lifestyle, and socio-economic conditions). This allowed us to justify the need for comprehensive treatment.

The study of an integrated approach to the treatment of heart failure, including modern methods of cardiology, pharmacotherapy, surgical interventions, rehabilitation and lifestyle changes in patients³.

The modern approach to the treatment of heart failure requires a multidisciplinary approach that integrates various therapeutic and preventive measures to maximize the effect. Let us consider the key elements of such an integrated approach. Modern cardiology techniques play a key role in diagnosis, treatment and monitoring of heart failure (HF). Advances in technology and clinical practice have led to significant improvements in the early detection of the disease and in the development of more accurate therapeutic strategies. Cardiology encompasses a wide range of diagnostic methods, therapeutic interventions and the application of innovative technologies to provide an individualized approach to each patient.

The following methods are used to accurately diagnose heart failure and assess the degree of cardiac dysfunction. Echocardiography (echocardiography) is the main tool for assessing the structure and function of the heart. This non-invasive method provides information on the size of the heart cavities, myocardial wall thickness, ejection fraction (a key indicator for the diagnosis of HF) and valve function. EchoCG is used to detect both systolic and diastolic dysfunction of the heart.

Cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the gold standard for accurate myocardial imaging, assessing myocardial structure and function, detecting scarring and evaluating myocardial perfusion. MRI is particularly useful when cardiomyopathy, myocarditis or ischemic lesions are suspected, which helps in diagnosing the causes of heart failure.

Cardiac computed tomography (CT) is a method used to visualize the coronary arteries and assess vessel calcification. This is important in determining the extent of atherosclerosis and the need for surgery such as coronary bypass or stenting.

Electrocardiography (ECG) is the standard method for assessing the electrical activity of the heart. ECG can detect arrhythmias, myocardial ischemia and signs of

ventricular overload, which may indicate the presence of HF.

Exercise tests (e.g. stress echocardiography or the treadmill test) assess the heart's response to exercise. These tests help to detect ischemia, reduce cardiac reserve and predict the risk of complications in patients with HF.

Cardiac catheterization is an invasive diagnostic method in which a catheter is inserted through the arteries to measure pressure in the chambers of the heart, assess cardiac output and the condition of the coronary arteries. This method may be necessary in complex cases to confirm the diagnosis and plan surgical interventions.

Based on data obtained from diagnostic methods, cardiologists develop a comprehensive therapeutic strategy for patients with heart failure. Both drug and non-drug therapies are currently available, including surgical and innovative interventions⁴.

Patients with chronic heart failure and low ejection fraction often develop arrhythmias that significantly worsen prognosis. Implantable devices such as pacemakers help to maintain a normal heart rhythm, and automatic defibrillators can prevent sudden death in dangerous arrhythmias.

Some patients with heart failure have dyssynchrony of ventricular contractions (irregular contractions), which reduces the efficiency of the heart. CRT is a procedure of placing a device that coordinates the contractions of the right and left ventricles, improving heart performance. Studies show that CRT significantly improves ejection fraction and reduces symptoms of HF⁵.

Modern cardiology is increasingly using minimally invasive techniques to treat structural heart disease that may contribute to heart failure. One of such methods is transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI), which is used in patients with severe aortic stenosis that is not amenable to drug treatment. TAVI can restore valve function without the need for open heart surgery, which is especially important for patients with high surgical risk.

Patients with HF are often diagnosed with CHD, which requires specialized treatment. Modern methods, such as balloon angioplasty and stenting, can improve coronary blood flow, thereby reducing the severity of heart failure and preventing the development of heart attacks.

Technological advances in cardiology offer new opportunities to improve the treatment of heart failure. Left Ventricular Assist Devices (VADs) are used in patients with severe heart failure who require temporary or permanent assistance in maintaining blood flow. These devices support or replace heart function, especially in patients awaiting transplantation⁶.

Modern technology makes it possible to use miniaturized devices for continuous monitoring of pulmonary artery

pressure, which helps in early diagnosis of exacerbations of HF and timely correction of treatment.

New methods of regenerative medicine are being explored, such as the use of stem cells and genetic therapy to repair damaged myocardium. Although these technologies are still at the stage of clinical trials, they represent great potential for the treatment of heart failure in the future.

Modern cardiology methods are also aimed at monitoring patients' condition and preventing exacerbations of HF. Telemedicine and remote monitoring help to track important patient parameters (e.g. blood pressure, heart rate, weight changes) in real time, allowing doctors to promptly adjust treatment and prevent hospitalizations.

Prevention of sudden cardiac death. Thanks to modern diagnostic methods, high-risk patients can be identified and prescribed devices to prevent sudden death (e.g. implantable cardioverter-defibrillators).

Thus, modern cardiology methods include both highly effective diagnostic technologies and therapeutic approaches aimed at correcting cardiac function, treating complications and improving prognosis. Integration of Cardiological methods in the complex treatment of heart failure is the most important aspect of improving clinical outcomes.

Pharmacotherapy is the cornerstone in the treatment of heart failure (HF) and is aimed at stabilizing the patient's condition, preventing disease progression, improving prognosis and quality of life. Progress in pharmacology has led to the development of a variety of drugs that affect various pathophysiological mechanisms of heart failure⁷. Complex drug therapy includes the use of several classes of drugs that reduce the load on the heart, improve hemodynamic and prevent pathological myocardial remodeling.

ACE inhibitors and angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs) are the mainstay of treatment for heart failure, especially when ejection fraction is reduced. These drugs block the conversion of angiotensin I to angiotensin II, which causes vasoconstriction, increases blood pressure and stimulates myocardial remodeling. ACE inhibitors reduce cardiac workload, decrease peripheral vascular resistance and slow the progression of myocardial remodeling, which helps to improve clinical outcomes in patients with HF.

In patients who cannot tolerate iAPPs because of cough or other side effects, angiotensin II receptor blockers are an alternative. BRAs (e.g. losartan, valsartan) block the action of angiotensin II directly at the receptors, which also prevents vasoconstriction and myocardial remodeling⁸.

Clinical trials have shown that these classes of drugs reduce mortality and hospitalization rates in patients with chronic heart failure, making them a key component of HF therapy.

Beta-blockers (e.g., bisoprolol, carvedilol, metoprolol) are another key class of drugs that have been shown to be effective in the treatment of heart failure. These drugs reduce heart rate and decrease myocardial workload, which helps to reduce oxygen consumption by the heart muscle and prevents further myocardial damage⁹.

Beta-blockers block adrenergic stimulation of β -receptors, which reduces the sympathetic activation seen in heart failure. This leads to a decrease in heart rate, improvement of diastolic function and a decrease in circulating catecholamine levels, which has a cardio protective effect.

Prolonged use of beta-blockers in patients with HF has been shown to reduce the incidence of complications, including sudden cardiac death and heart attacks. However, the administration of these drugs should be done with caution, starting with low doses, as a sharp decrease in sympathetic system activity may worsen symptoms in the initial stages of treatment.

Mineral corticoid receptor antagonists (e.g., spironolactone, eplerenone) are used to block the action of aldosterone, a hormone that stimulates sodium and water retention in the body and promotes myocardial and vascular remodeling. MRAs block aldosterone receptors, reducing sodium and water retention in the body, resulting in a decrease in circulating blood volume and the workload of the heart. These drugs also have an antiremodelling effect on the myocardium, preventing its fibrosis and stiffness¹⁰.

Mineral corticoid antagonists have been shown to reduce mortality and hospitalization rates in patients with severe heart failure. Spironolactone and eplerenone are particularly effective in patients with an ejection fraction below 35% who are already prescribed ACE inhibitors or ARBs and beta-blockers.

Diuretics play an important role in treating the symptoms of heart failure, especially when there is oedema and fluid stasis in the lungs and other organs. These drugs help to control the amount of fluid in the body, which relieves symptoms of stasis and improves the patient's general well-being.

Loop diuretics (e.g., furosemide) quickly and effectively eliminate excess fluid, reducing pressure in the pulmonary circulation and improving breathing in patients with acute decompensated HF. Thiazide diuretics are often used in combination with loop diuretics to enhance the diuretic effect, especially in treatment-resistant patients.

Potassium-saving diuretics, such as spironolactone (also classified as an AMR), help prevent hypokalaemia that can occur with other diuretics. However, it should be remembered that diuretics do not have a significant effect on patient survival, so their main role is to improve symptomatology and fluid control¹¹.

SGLT2 inhibitors, originally developed for the treatment of type 2 diabetes, have proven highly effective in improving clinical outcomes in patients with heart failure, both with preserved and reduced ejection fraction. These drugs block glucose reabsorption in the kidneys, resulting in glucosuria and a mild diuretic effect. In addition, SGLT2 inhibitors influence metabolism, reduce blood pressure, decrease circulating blood volume and have a positive effect on the vascular system and myocardium.

Studies have shown that drugs in this group (e.g. dapagliflozin, empagliflozin) reduce the risk of cardiovascular death and the frequency of hospitalizations for heart failure. This class of drugs has shown good results in patients with and without diabetes, making them an important component of HF therapy.

Vasodilators such as nitrates and hydralazine reduce cardiac workload by dilating vessels and reducing venous return, which improves hemodynamic. They are particularly effective in patients with high blood pressure and HF. Hydralazine and isosorbide dinitrate can also be administered to patients who cannot tolerate ACE inhibitors or angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARB).

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Digoxin, a cardiac glycoside, can be used to control heart rate in patients with chronic HF and atrial fibrillation. However, its use is limited due to the narrow therapeutic window and the risk of intoxication.

Surgical interventions play a key role in the treatment of heart failure (HF), especially in patients with severe forms of disease that do not respond to drug therapy. Current surgical approaches range from minimally invasive procedures to complex operations such as heart transplantation. Surgical treatment can be aimed either at eliminating the cause of heart failure (e.g., correction of valve pathology) or at mechanically supporting cardiac function (e.g., implantation of assist devices). Let us consider the main directions of surgical treatment of heart failure¹².

Heart valve abnormalities (e.g. mitral, aortic) are one of the leading causes of heart failure. Valve defects can lead to overloading of the heart chambers, which ultimately causes heart dysfunction.

One of the most common methods of valve pathology treatment is replacement of the damaged valve with an artificial prosthesis. Modern prostheses are of two types: mechanical and biological. Mechanical valves have a long service life but require constant intake of anticoagulants to prevent thrombosis. Biological prostheses are made from animal tissue and have a lower risk of thrombosis but require replacement after 10-15 years.

Valve grafting (reconstruction) allows the patient's own valves to be preserved and their function restored. For example, mitral plasty may involve correcting the shape of the valve annulus or suturing excess flap tissue. This approach is less invasive than complete valve replacement and reduces the risk of complications associated with prostheses.

Tran catheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI) is a minimally invasive procedure in which a new valve is inserted through a catheter without the need for open surgery. TAVI is recommended for patients with severe aortic stenosis and high surgical risk, especially the elderly and patients with co morbidities.

A significant number of patients with heart failure have impaired synchronization of ventricular contractions (dyssynchrony), which significantly impairs the efficiency of the heart. Resynchronization therapy (CRT) aims to coordinate right and left ventricular contractions and improve the pumping function of the heart.

Installation of a special device (pacemaker) helps to restore synchronization of contractions by delivering electrical impulses to certain areas of the myocardium. This procedure is effective in patients with chronic heart failure who have dyssynchrony and reduced ejection fraction¹³.

Clinical trials have shown that CRT improves clinical outcomes, increases ejection fraction, reduces symptoms of heart failure and decreases hospitalization rates. This method can significantly improve the quality of life of patients who are not helped by standard drug therapies.

For patients with severe chronic heart failure, when heart function is significantly reduced and drug treatment no longer works, mechanical assistive devices are used to support or replace left ventricular function.

Left Ventricular Assist Devices (VADs) are used to support cardiac function in patients with severe heart failure. VADs help pump blood from the left ventricle to the aorta, ensuring normal perfusion of organs and tissues. VADs were originally used as a temporary measure for patients awaiting heart transplantation ("bridge to transplantation"), but now these devices are also used as a permanent therapy for patients who cannot undergo transplantation.

Indications for VADs include patients with end-stage HF who have significant left ventricular dysfunction despite maximal drug therapy. These devices can significantly

improve survival and quality of life in patients who previously had a severely unfavorable prognosis.

In rare cases, when both ventricles of the heart cease to function, a fully artificial heart can be implanted to temporarily fulfill myocardial function while the patient awaits transplantation¹⁴.

Modern cardiac surgery is increasingly using minimally invasive techniques that reduce surgical risks and speed up patient recovery. In recent years, the following minimally invasive methods have been developed for the treatment of heart failure.

Rehabilitation and lifestyle modification are the most important aspects of a comprehensive approach to the treatment of heart failure (HF). The inclusion of non-medication methods, such as regular physical activity, nutritional correction, psycho-emotional support and avoidance of bad habits, significantly improves the prognosis of the disease and the quality of life of patients. These measures not only complement drug therapy but also help to reduce the risks of recurrent exacerbations and complications¹⁵.

Cardiac rehabilitation is a set of measures aimed at restoring a patient's physical and psycho-emotional state after an exacerbation of heart failure or surgical interventions. The most successful cardiac rehabilitation programmes include supervised exercise, nutritional and self-management education, and psychological support. These programmes are tailored to the individual needs of each patient, depending on the stage of heart failure and general health.

Regular physical activity is a key element in the rehabilitation of patients with HF. It helps to improve exercise tolerance, reduce symptoms such as breathlessness and fatigue, and strengthen the heart muscle. Studies show that moderate aerobic exercise such as walking, swimming or cycling improves cardiovascular function and reduces the risk of re-hospitalization.

Exercise programmes are designed individually for each patient, taking into account fitness level and stage of CHF. Patients with severe heart failure can start with light exercise under specialist supervision, gradually increasing in intensity¹⁶.

Studies show that regular physical activity reduces the incidence of hospitalization, improves left ventricular function, reduces the risk of cardiovascular events and increases the life expectancy of patients with chronic heart failure.

Nutritional correction and adherence to special dietary recommendations play an important role in the control of heart failure. Excessive salt, fat and calorie intake exacerbates HF symptoms by increasing the burden on the heart and contributing to oedema.

Reducing salt intake is one of the basic principles of nutritional therapy in heart failure. Sodium intake should be limited to 2-3 grams per day, as excess salt contributes to fluid retention in the body and worsens symptoms of stasis, such as oedema and dyspnoea. Being overweight is a significant risk factor for heart failure patients, as it increases the workload on the heart and worsens symptoms. Weight control helps to improve the patient's overall health and reduces the likelihood of recurrent exacerbations.

For patients with HF, a diet limiting saturated fats and cholesterol is recommended to help prevent further development of atherosclerosis and other cardiovascular diseases. At the same time, emphasis is placed on the consumption of polyunsaturated fatty acids, fiber and complex carbohydrates.

Psychological stress, depression and anxiety disorders are common among patients with heart failure and can have a negative impact on treatment outcomes. Psycho-emotional support is an integral part of rehabilitation, as the patient's emotional well-being is closely linked to physical health.

Depressive and anxiety disorders are common in patients with HF, which can reduce compliance (adherence to medical recommendations) and impair quality of life. Psychological counseling, cognitive-behavioral therapy and family support play an important role in the rehabilitation of patients, helping to reduce stress and improve emotional well-being.

Relaxation techniques such as meditation, yoga, deep breathing and progressive muscle relaxation can significantly reduce stress levels and promote physical well-being. Regular practice of these techniques helps patients to control emotional reactions to illness and improves well-being¹⁷.

Lifestyle changes involve avoiding habits that can worsen the course of heart failure. These habits include smoking, alcohol abuse and physical inactivity. Smoking is one of the most significant risk factors for the development and progression of heart failure. Nicotine causes vasoconstriction and increases the workload of the heart, worsening the symptoms of the disease. Complete smoking cessation reduces the risk of cardiovascular complications and improves patient prognosis.

Moderate alcohol consumption may be acceptable for patients with heart failure, but alcohol abuse significantly increases the risk of cardiomyopathy and worsens the course of the disease. For patients with severe HF, complete avoidance of alcohol is recommended.

Lifestyle change is a long-term process that requires consistency and support from physicians, family members and the community. Rehabilitation programmes should be personalized and tailored to the patient's individual needs, lifestyle, physical activity level and emo-

tional state. A balanced combination of physical activity, nutritional therapy, psychological support and avoidance of bad habits can not only improve the prognosis of heart failure but also improve the patient's quality of life in the long term¹⁸.

Thus, rehabilitation and lifestyle changes are an important part of a comprehensive approach to the treatment of heart failure. They help to stabilize the condition, prevent exacerbations and help patients lead an active and full life.

Despite significant advances in the diagnosis and management of heart failure (HF), there are a number of issues and challenges that can hamper the effectiveness of treatment and impair patients' quality of life. In this section, we review the key challenges associated with the treatment of HF, including lack of patient compliance, complex clinical scenarios, lack of access to specialized care and challenges in monitoring and rehabilitation.

Patient compliance (or adherence) is one of the biggest challenges in the management of heart failure. Low compliance can lead to worsening of patients' condition, increased hospitalizations and even premature death.

The main reasons for low compliance include:

- Complexity of the treatment regimen and a large number of medications, which makes adherence difficult;
- Side effects of medications, which can cause dissatisfaction in patients and reduce motivation to continue therapy;
- Lack of adequate information about the disease and the importance of adherence to medical recommendations.

To increase compliance, it is possible to use:

- Educational programmes that help patients understand the nature of the disease and the importance of treatment;
- Simplifying treatment regimens where possible to reduce the number of medications taken;
- Regular telephone calls or visits to monitor condition and provide support¹⁹.

Heart failure can be combined with other diseases, making treatment more complex. Co morbid conditions such as diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease,

renal failure and arterial hypertension require a comprehensive approach to therapy and may influence the choice of medication.

Some drugs used for the treatment of HF may be contraindicated or require dose adjustment in the presence of certain co morbidities. For example, the use of diuretics in patients with renal failure may cause deterioration of renal function, and the use of beta-blockers in patients with asthma may provoke an exacerbation.

Effective treatment of patients with heart failure and co morbid conditions requires a multidisciplinary approach involving cardiologists, internists, endocrinologists, nephrologists, and other specialists. This helps provide an individualized approach and improve outcomes of treatment.

Many patients with heart failure face problems accessing specialized medical care, which can significantly worsen their prognosis.

In rural and remote areas, access to specialized care may be limited. This leads to delayed diagnosis, inadequate symptom control and lack of appropriate rehabilitation measures²⁰.

The high cost of treatment and lack of insurance can prevent patients from getting the care they need, which is especially true for patients in need of expensive medications and procedures.

Measures are needed to improve access to health care services, such as the development of telemedicine, which allows patients to be consulted and monitored remotely. The introduction of funding and support programmes for heart failure patients is also an important step.

Monitoring patients with heart failure and implementing rehabilitation programmes are important aspects of an integrated approach to care, but they also face a number of challenges. There are not always clear protocols and standards for monitoring patients. This can result in patients not receiving the attention and support they need during treatment.

Rehabilitation programmes are often not adequately funded, which limits their accessibility for many patients. This also applies to the lack of qualified staff and infrastructure to run rehabilitation programmes.

The introduction of technology to monitor patients' condition (e.g. wearable devices, symptom tracking apps) can help to better monitor patients' condition and improve their engagement in treatment. However, this requires accessibility and patient understanding of the technology.

The psycho-emotional state of patients with heart failure is also an important aspect that can complicate treatment. Depression, anxiety and stress can significantly impair quality of life and reduce the effectiveness of therapy²¹.

Depressive disorders are common in patients with heart failure and can interfere with treatment adherence. They also affect general health, which may lead to worsening of disease symptoms.

It is important that the treatment of heart failure includes psychological support and treatment of associated psycho-emotional disorders. Psychotherapy, support groups and pharmacotherapy can have a significant impact on improving the overall condition of patients.

Lack of knowledge about the disease and its treatment can significantly affect the results of therapy. Patients who do not understand the nature of their disease and the importance of treatment often do not adhere to medical recommendations. Educational activities for patients and their families can significantly increase understanding of heart failure and the importance of treatment adherence. Such programmes should include information about the disease, treatment options, nutritional therapy, physical activity and stress management²².

The use of digital platforms and mobile applications for patient education can significantly improve the availability of information and patient engagement in treatment. This can also include reminders to take medication and make appointments with doctors.

In summary, the treatment of heart failure faces many issues and challenges that require an integrated approach and multidisciplinary collaboration. Removing barriers in access to care, improving patient compliance, implementing modern monitoring technologies and educational programmes will help to improve outcomes and quality of life for patients with heart failure. The development and implementation of new strategies in treatment and rehabilitation will help to effectively address emerging problems and provide maximum support to patients.

Conclusions

Treatment of heart failure (HF) is a complex and multifaceted process that requires integration of various medical disciplines and approaches. As a result of the analysis, several key conclusions about the integrated approach to the treatment of this serious pathology can be highlighted.

Heart failure requires a comprehensive approach, including pharmacotherapy, surgery, rehabilitation and lifestyle changes. Effective treatment is not limited to the prescription of medications, but also includes continuous monitoring of the patient's condition, as well as the involvement of a multidisciplinary team of specialists. Modern therapies such as the use of angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEIs), beta-adrenoblockers, mineral corticoid receptor antagonists (MCRAs) and new classes of drugs (e.g. SGLT2 inhibitors) are significantly improving patient outcomes and quality of life. These drugs contribute to a reduction in mortality and hospitalization rates.

Low levels of patient compliance remain a major barrier to successful treatment. Education programmes and support systems can help to improve patient adherence to therapy, thereby improving treatment outcomes. The existence of co morbidities requires an individualized approach to therapy. A multidisciplinary approach involving collaboration between different specialists is essential to optimize treatment and management of co-morbid conditions.

Many patients face difficulties in accessing specialized care due to geographical and financial barriers. The development of telemedicine and funding programmes can improve the situation and provide the necessary support to patients, especially in remote regions.

Rehabilitation of patients with heart failure plays an important role in their recovery and improved quality of life. The need for standardized monitoring and rehabilitation programmes, as well as the use of technology to track patients' condition, underlines the importance of a comprehensive approach. The psycho-emotional state of patients also has a significant impact on treatment outcomes. Incorporating psychological support and therapies to manage stress and depression into the overall treatment plan will help to improve quality of life and increase adherence to therapy.

Thus, a comprehensive approach to the treatment of heart failure involves a combination of medical, educational and psycho-emotional interventions. As heart failure represents one of the leading causes of death worldwide, it is important to continue to develop and implement new therapies to improve patients' quality of

life and adherence to therapy. Successful treatment of heart failure requires attention to every detail, which will ultimately significantly improve the prognosis and quality of life of patients.

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